

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

L.A.Izzatullayev

THIN FIBER COTTON IN EXTREME CLIMATES THE EFFECT OF STEMTHICKNESS AND

PRUNING ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF THE TERMIZ-202VARIETY

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/OKTABR

